

Improved ORR Activity and Long-Term Durability of Pt Nanoparticles Deposited on TiO₂-Decorated Multiwall Carbon Nanotubes

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Titanium dioxide coatings of different thicknesses were deposited on the acid-treated multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) using controlled atomic layer deposition (ALD). Pt nanoparticles (NP) were deposited on TiO₂/MWCNT supports using two deposition methods, viz. sputter-deposition and photo-deposition. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) measurements revealed successful application of ALD for the deposition of TiO₂. Both magnetron sputtering and photo-deposition were found to be efficient and well-controlled techniques for the deposition of Pt NPs on oxide-carbon support. Electrochemical decontamination and characterization of the catalysts surface was carried out by CO stripping and cyclic voltammetry in 0.1 M KOH solution. The prepared Pt-TiO₂/MWCNT catalyst showed comparable oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) activity to that of commercial Pt/C (20 wt%), while long-term durability test revealed better durability of the prepared catalysts due to strong metal-support interaction.

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In order to solve the global environmental problems regarding energy production, the proton-exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cell is considered as one of the most promising green and sustainable energy conversion devices mainly because of its simple and clean operating system, low working temperature and high power density.¹ Pt-based catalysts have been extensively investigated in the past few decades due to their remarkable electrocatalytic activity toward the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) at fuel cell cathode.²⁻⁴ The mainstream research dedicated to this area includes minimizing the loading of Pt in the fuel cell stacks and improving its electrocatalytic activity.⁵⁻⁷ A common approach to achieve these goals is depositing highly dispersed platinum nanoparticles (NPs) on a suitable support material, typically high-area carbon-based supports such as Vulcan carbon, graphene nanosheets, carbon nanotubes (CNT) and carbon nanofibers.⁸⁻¹⁰ Multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) are preferred support material for Pt NPs because of their outstanding chemical, structural and mechanical properties and remarkable electrical conductivity.¹¹⁻¹³ Stability of the supported Pt NPs in the fuel cell operating conditions is another challenging aspect for the researchers because of the degradation of the catalyst nanoparticles and/or the carbon support.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ Several metal oxides such as MoO_x, NbO_x, W_xO_y, Ti_xO_y, CeO_x and SnO_x have been introduced by many research groups as supplementary coating to inhibit catalyst degradation.¹⁸⁻²¹ For example, Ji et al. have recently demonstrated better durability of the Pt/TiO₂ catalyst supported on CNTs as compared to that of Pt/C, which can be attributed to the strong metal-support interaction (SMSI).²² TiO₂ nano/sub-nano particles have also been used to block the micropores in commercial carbon black by a decomposition adsorption method.²³ The prepared support showed better durability in addition to efficient utilization of the metal electrocatalyst. Meng and Tang also reported Pt/TiO₂ supported on carbon nitride (CN_x) nanofibers as a durable catalyst toward the ORR in comparison to Pt/C.²⁴ The Pt/TiO₂-CN_x catalyst retained more catalytic activity than that of the Pt/C after 5000 potential cycles. Our group has previously investigated electrocatalytic activity of Pt NPs chemically deposited on TiO₂-graphene composite toward O₂ reduction.²⁵ The catalyst revealed higher electrocatalytic activity toward the electroreduction of O₂ with typical four-electron pathway, which could be ascribed to the uniformly deposited Pt NPs on the TiO₂-functionalized graphene nanosheets. However, durability of the catalyst was lower than that of the Pt/C.

Among the several possible techniques, some groups suggested atomic layer deposition (ALD) as an appropriate tool for the deposition of metal oxides on a substrate.²⁶⁻³⁰ Influence of defects in vertically-aligned CNTs on the deposition of TiO₂ using the ALD method has been investigated.³¹ It was observed that nucleation of the nanoparticles depends on the availability of the heteroatoms on the support surface rather than structural defects. TiO₂ films were also grown on graphene and CNTs using the ALD method.³² Al₂O₃ ultrathin film was introduced as an adhesion layer in order to get conformal TiO₂ thin films. Chung et al. have reported that Pt/C catalysts coated with TiO₂ by ALD are more durable in PEM fuel cell than Pt/C catalyst.³³ The electrocatalytic activity and long-term stability of the Pt NPs sputter-deposited on TiO₂-decorated vertically-aligned MWCNTs have been investigated by our group previously.³⁴ The prepared catalyst exhibited comparable electrocatalytic activity and durability to that of the Pt/C (20 wt%) catalyst. It has also been reported by other groups that magnetron sputtering is a well-controlled technique for the deposition of Pt nanoparticles on the substrate.^{35,36} The electroreduction of O₂ on Pt-Ni alloys prepared by controlled sputter-deposition and its dependence on the composition and electronic structure of the catalyst was investigated by Watanabe and co-workers.³⁷ They reported maximum ORR activity at ca. 30% of Ni content while the active electrocatalytic surfaces were entirely covered by Pt NPs. Srinivasan and co-workers reported improved ORR kinetics in the case of sputter-deposited Pt/C with 4-fold increase in the current density in comparison to that of the non-sputtered one, while the reaction pathway was the same for both types of electrocatalysts.³⁸ Our group has previously reported sputter-deposition of Pt NPs on MWCNTs.³⁹⁻⁴¹ The SEM results revealed uniform deposition of the nanoparticles on the support surface, which resulted into improved electrocatalytic activity of the Pt/MWCNT catalysts than that of the commercial Pt/C (20 wt%, E-TEK). Photo-deposition is another useful technique used for the deposition of Pt nanoparticles preferably on the metal oxide of the oxide-carbon composite as reported previously.⁴² Investigations have revealed that the catalyst nanoparticles photo-deposited on metal oxide are more resistant to degradation because of the selective deposition on metal oxide and anchoring mechanism initiated by UV photons. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis confirms electronic modification of the catalytic centers that results into the SMSI.^{43,44}

The present work is focused on the comparison of sputter-deposition and photo-deposition of Pt NPs on TiO₂/CNT composite. Physicochemical and electrochemical characterization are carried out

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to investigate surface morphology of the catalysts and metal-support interaction at the interface. The prepared Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts are compared in terms of the O₂ electroreduction activity and stability in alkaline media.

Experimental

Atomic layer deposition of titanium dioxide on CNTs.—A glass vial containing acid-treated multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs, >95%, diameter 30 ± 10 nm, Nanolab, Brighton, MA, USA) dispersed in 2-propanol (1 mg mL⁻¹) was put in ultrasonic bath for 30 min to get a homogeneous suspension. 100 μL of the suspension was transferred to the polished glassy carbon (GC) plate (surface area (*A*) = 5 cm²) 5 times for uniform coating of the surface and dried at 60°C in the oven for 5 min. TiO₂ NPs were deposited on the GC plates coated with MWCNTs using the ALD method. Two thicknesses of TiO₂ i.e. 35 and 50 ALD cycles were applied for comparison. The prepared TiO₂/CNT composites were then dispersed in 2-propanol (1 mg mL⁻¹) followed by sonication for 15 min.

Deposition of Pt nanoparticles on TiO₂/CNT composites.—For sputter-deposition of Pt NPs, polished GC electrodes (*A* = 0.126 cm²), modified with TiO₂/CNT composites were subjected to the sputtering chamber. The nominal thicknesses and loadings of Pt coatings obtained were 4 nm (8.6 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²), 8 nm (17.2 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²) and 12 nm (25.8 μg_{Pt} cm⁻²). The electrodes prepared by sputter-deposition were labelled as “xPt-yTiO₂/CNT”, where “x” shows the nominal thickness of the deposited Pt (4, 8 and 12 nm), while “y” represents thickness of TiO₂ coating in terms of number of ALD cycles (35 and 50). For comparison, Pt NPs were photo-deposited on 35TiO₂/CNT. Briefly, the photochemical cell containing support material suspended in Milli-Q water was placed in front of the UV/Vis beam with constant nitrogen purging. Calculated amount of chloroplatinic acid (H₂PtCl₆·6H₂O, Alfa Aesar) was dissolved in 2-propanol and added to the suspension. UV/Vis light was allowed to enter the cell for 1 h. The prepared catalyst (designated as Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT) was then washed with Milli-Q water, vacuum filtered and dried overnight in the oven. Pt loading in Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT catalysts was calculated to be 20 μg_{Pt} cm⁻².

Instrumentation and measurements.—The ALD process was performed in a PICOSUN R-200 Advanced ALD reactor (Picosun Oy, Finland). Temperature of the substrate was kept constant at 250°C. TiCl₄ (99.9%, Aldrich) and deionized water were used as precursors. Dry nitrogen (100-110 Pa) was introduced as a carrier and purging gas. The vapors of the precursors introduced alternatively into the deposition chamber were controlled by pneumatic valves. For sputter-deposition of Pt, DC-magnetron sputtering was performed at room temperature using pure planar round Pt target (99.99%) and pure argon (99.999%). In the sputtering chamber, the pressure was kept constant (3 × 10⁻³ mbar) and a DC-power of 2 W was applied. The nominal thickness of Pt was determined by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometer (Rigaku ZSX 400).

The UV/Vis source used for the photo-deposition of Pt was a Xe-lamp of 159 W. The visible/infrared light was filtered by a hot mirror filter fitted at the entrance of the photochemical cell while a water filter (long-pass filter GG40) was applied between the UV/Vis source and the cell to keep the sample cool during the photochemical reaction.

Surface morphology of the prepared catalysts were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using Helios NanoLab 600 (FEI) microscope and high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) and elemental mapping using Titan 200 instrument (FEI) fitted with 4 sensors Super-X EDX system (FEI/Bruker). Further investigation of the catalyst surface was carried out by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a SCI-ENTA SES-100 electron spectrometer. A non-monochromatized Mg Ka (incident energy 1253.6 eV) X-ray source (400 W) was applied and the takeoff angle was 90°. The energy range for collecting the

survey spectra was 600-0 eV with a pass energy of 200 eV and step size of 0.5 eV.

All the electrochemical measurements were carried out in alkaline media (0.1 M KOH solution) using the standard 3-electrode electrochemical cell. Pt wire was used as counter electrode and a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) was connected as reference electrode. The measurements were monitored and controlled by Autolab potentiostat/galvanostat PGSTAT30 (Metrohm Autolab B.V., The Netherlands). For the electrochemical decontamination and surface characterization, CO stripping experiments were performed on all the prepared catalysts. In these experiments, CO was first adsorbed at the electrode surface at 0.1 V vs RHE for 30 s. The pre-adsorbed CO was then removed from the electrode surface by potential cycling (0.05–1.0 V) at 20 mV s⁻¹, after purging with Ar for 30 min. Further electrochemical characterization of the catalysts surface were carried out by measuring cyclic voltammetry (CV) in Ar-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution. The ORR activity of the Pt/TiO₂-CNT catalysts was investigated by rotating disk electrode (RDE) composed of a CTV101 speed control unit (Radiometer) and an EDI101 rotator. Long-term durability of the catalyst was investigated by measuring 10,000 repetitive cycles in Ar-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution (0.6 to 1.0 V vs RHE) at 100 mV s⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical characterization of the catalysts.—Figure 1 reveals that the surface morphology of Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts remarkably depends on the metal oxide coating on the CNT surface and Pt deposition method. SEM image of the prepared catalysts in Figure 1a shows platinum photo-deposited on 35TiO₂/CNT while Figures 1b–1d represents 4, 8 and 12 nm of Pt sputter-deposited on 35TiO₂/CNT surface, respectively. It is observed that in the case of photo-deposition, Pt NPs deposit selectively on the metal-oxide coating that results in the formation of smaller agglomerates of various size and shape. This indicates that the particle-size distribution of photo-deposited Pt nanoparticles mainly depends on the TiO₂ coating. In the case of 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT, the Pt NPs are uniformly distributed on the support surface and thus confirms better metal utilization and metal-support interaction, which in turn, increases electroactive surface area and the ORR electrocatalytic activity of the electrode. Higher loading of sputter-deposited Pt results in the formation of bigger nanoparticles (Figures 1c and 1d) which may have a negative effect on the metal-support interaction and electrocatalytic activity of the Pt catalyst.⁴¹

Figure 2 shows HAADF-STEM image of 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT catalysts. It is seen that the nanotubes are fully covered with titania ALD film having Pt NPs on it. The elemental mappings given in the same image clearly show distribution of the Pt nanoparticles and uniform TiO₂ coating on the surface of CNTs. It should be noted that relatively tightly lying particles of Pt metal absorb part of Ti K_α radiation generated by probe electrons in the underlying TiO₂ film. For that reason, the X-ray signal of Ti is less intense as it would be without Pt addition. Moreover, it is observed that magnetron sputtering results in uniform distribution of Pt NPs on the TiO₂ coated MWCNTs while photo-deposition leads to the formation of smaller agglomerates at the support surface as seen in SEM analysis (Figure 1a). This can be attributed to the anchoring mechanism of photo-deposition where metal oxide acts as nucleation site for the deposition of Pt NPs.

Surface chemistry of the prepared catalysts, elemental composition and electronic states of Pt and Ti were investigated by the XPS analysis. The XPS survey spectrum of Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst is presented in Figure 3. The peaks at 71.0 and 74.5 eV correspond to Pt4f while those at 458.5 and 464.5 eV correspond to Ti2p. C1s main peak is located at 284.5 eV and O1s peak appears at 530.5 eV. The smaller peaks located at 314.5 and 332.0 eV correspond to Pt4d. The Pt4f and Ti2p deconvoluted XPS peaks are shown in the insets. The peak centered at 71.0 eV corresponds to Pt⁰ 4f_{7/2} and a small peak at 74.5 eV to Pt⁴⁺ 4f_{7/2} indicating that platinum partially exists in two oxidation

Figure 1. SEM images of (a) Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT (b) 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT (c) 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and (d) 12Pt-35TiO₂/CNT samples.

states. Titanium is in the Ti⁴⁺ state (TiO₂). XPS results for Pt sputter-deposited on TiO₂/CNT composite have been reported earlier.⁴¹

Electrochemical characterization of catalysts.—The CO electro-oxidation profile of 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst is presented in Figure 4a wherein the first cycle from 0.05 to 0.4 V confirms blocking of the catalytic surface with CO followed by broad CO-oxidation peaks (0.5–0.7 V) in the second cycle. Absence of the CO oxidation peak in the third potential cycle confirms that the pre-adsorbed CO monolayer is now completely oxidized. As demonstrated in Figure 4b, all prepared catalysts show similar CO stripping profiles and the onset potential for all catalysts is ~0.38 V. All the catalysts show a CO oxidation main peak at ~0.67 V and a small peak at ~0.58 V. CO oxidation on supported Pt-based catalysts is an important tool for the evaluation of the SMSI at the interface.⁴⁵ A comparison of the normalized CO oxidation peaks, shown in the inset of Figure 4b illustrates that the CO oxidation main peaks on 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT, 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT and Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT are located at 0.674, 0.662 and 0.657 V, respectively. The relative negative shift in the CO oxidation peaks corresponds to the

strength of metal-support interaction at the interface.⁴⁶ Comparing CO stripping peak potentials of 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT to 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT indicates that the thickness of TiO₂ coating with respect to Pt loading affects the extent of the metal-support interaction. Further negative shift for Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT indicates relatively stronger metal-support interaction that can be ascribed to the anchoring mechanism of Pt NPs to the oxide-carbon composite. The pre-peak at approximately 0.5 V observed at relatively higher Pt loading can be attributed to agglomeration of the nanoparticles.⁴⁷ The difference in the peaks height is ascribed to the different Pt loading and surface morphology of the catalysts.⁴⁸

Figure 5 shows the stable cyclic voltammograms recorded in 0.1 M KOH after cleaning the catalyst surface by CO stripping. The hydrogen desorption peaks at 0.28 and 0.38 V in the anodic sweep showed the presence of (110) and (100) facets, respectively.^{39,49–51} The real surface area (*A_r*) of the Pt catalyst was determined from the desorption peaks.⁵² As presented in Table 1, the highest *A_r* value of 1.06 cm² is shown by Pt photo-deposited on 35TiO₂/CNT (PD). However, catalysts prepared by magnetron sputtering showed much smaller surface

Figure 2. HAADF-STEM images of 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT samples with corresponding elemental mappings of Pt and Ti.

areas, which may be due to the compact deposition of Pt nanoparticles on the support surface as observed in Figures 1b–1d and 2a. For example, 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst had the lowest value of A_r (0.18 cm²) attributed to the relatively low Pt loading. Expectedly, the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT catalysts had nearly the same A_r values of 0.31 and 0.32 cm², respectively. A slight increase was observed for 12Pt-35TiO₂/CNT ($A_r = 0.37$ cm²). Commercial Pt/C (20 wt%) catalyst showed a higher surface area of Pt ($A_r = 0.86$ cm²). The surface areas of all catalysts were also determined from the CO oxidation peaks as presented in Table I. These values were found close to those determined from the hydrogen desorption peaks.

Oxygen reduction reaction studies.—Figure 6 displays the RDE polarization curves of the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst measured at various electrode rotation speeds. The diffusion-limited current density values determined from the anodic sweeps are close to the theoretical ones. The Koutecky-Levich (K-L) plots were constructed from the RDE data and the number of electrons (n) involved in the reaction were determined using Eq. 1.⁵³

$$\frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{j_k} + \frac{1}{j_d} = -\frac{1}{nFkC_{O_2}^b} - \frac{1}{0.62nFD_{O_2}^{2/3}v^{-1/6}C_{O_2}^b\omega^{1/2}} \quad [1]$$

Table I. Kinetic parameters for oxygen reduction reaction on Pt-TiO₂/MWCNT catalysts in 0.1 M KOH solution.

Electrode	A_r (cm ²) by H _{UPD}	A_r (cm ²) by CO oxidation	ECSA (m ² g ⁻¹ _{Pt})	Tafel slope (mV) I region*	Tafel slope (mV) II region*	$E_{1/2}$ (V)	SA at 0.9 V (mA cm ⁻²)	MA at 0.9 V (A g ⁻¹)
4Pt-35TiO ₂ /CNT	0.18 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	16 ± 1	-55 ± 3	-121 ± 2	0.80 ± 0.01	0.22 ± 0.01	36 ± 1
8Pt-35TiO ₂ /CNT	0.31 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	15 ± 2	-55 ± 5	-121 ± 4	0.79 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.01	22 ± 1
8Pt-50TiO ₂ /CNT	0.32 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.02	15 ± 2	-60 ± 2	-122 ± 2	0.81 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	25 ± 2
12Pt-35TiO ₂ /CNT	0.37 ± 0.01	0.39 ± 0.01	11 ± 2	-61 ± 3	-126 ± 4	0.84 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.02	38 ± 1
Pt _{PD} -35TiO ₂ /CNT	1.06 ± 0.02	1.02 ± 0.02	39 ± 3	-61 ± 4	-124 ± 5	0.86 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.01	124 ± 2
Commercial Pt/C	0.86 ± 0.01	0.85 ± 0.01	32 ± 4	-64 ± 5	-120 ± 2	0.84 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.01	62 ± 1

*Region I corresponds to low current densities and region II to high current densities.

Figure 3. XPS spectra of Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst. The inset shows deconvoluted peaks of Pt4f and Ti2p.

where j is the experimentally measured current density at an applied potential, while j_k and j_d represent the kinetic current density and diffusion-limited current density, respectively. F is the Faraday constant ($96,485 \text{ C mol}^{-1}$), k represents the electrochemical rate constant for O₂ reduction, $C_{O_2}^b$ is the concentration of O₂ in the bulk of solution ($1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol cm}^{-3}$),⁵⁴ while D_{O_2} denotes the diffusion coefficient of O₂ ($1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).⁵⁴ ν is the kinetic viscosity of the

Figure 4. CO stripping voltammograms of (a) 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and (b) comparison of CO stripping peaks of Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts in Ar-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution, the inset shows normalized CO stripping peaks on Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT, 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT.

Figure 5. CV curves of Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts in Ar-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution ($\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$).

electrolyte solution ($0.01 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$),⁵⁵ and ω is the electrode rotation speed (rad s^{-1}). As shown in the inset of Figure 6, the n value is close to four revealing that the catalyst followed a typical 4-electron ORR pathway for the whole range of potentials studied. Similar n value for TiO₂ supported Pt catalysts have been reported earlier.^{34,56,57} Four-electron reduction of oxygen was also reported previously for Pt-TiO₂ catalysts in 0.1 M KOH solution.⁵⁸ However, Kim et al. have shown the n value close to 3 for Pt deposited on rutile TiO₂.⁵⁹ According to them, treatment of TiO₂ support improves the ORR kinetics.

Figure 7a displays the RDE polarization curves (1900 rpm) of all the prepared catalysts in comparison to that of the Pt/C catalyst. The half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) values, for all the electrodes are summarized in Table I. The highest $E_{1/2}$ value of 0.86 V is shown by Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT. In the case of sputter-deposited Pt, 12Pt-35TiO₂/CNT showed similar $E_{1/2}$ value to that of the Pt/C (0.84 V). Nevertheless, 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT, 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT catalysts showed relatively lower $E_{1/2}$ of $0.80 \pm 0.10 \text{ V}$. The highest ORR activity of Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT can be explained on the basis of the increased electronic cloud on the catalytic center as a result of SMSI.⁴³

It has been observed earlier that the interfacial interaction between the Ti atoms and the supported Pt catalyst in Pt/TiO₂ system increases electronic density on the catalyst, which results into improved ORR activity.^{43,60} Hwang and co-workers have also revealed electronic modification of the Pt catalyst as a result of synergistic interaction with Ti_{0.7}Mo_{0.3}O₂ support.⁶¹ Moreover, the ORR activity of

Figure 6. ORR polarization curves for 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst recorded at different electrode rotation speeds ($\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$) in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution. The inset shows n value.

Figure 7. (a) Comparison of ORR polarization curves of Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts and Pt/C recorded at 1900 rpm in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution and (b) Tafel plots for ORR on Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts.

8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT is moderately higher than that of the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT counterpart, which further justifies the metal-support interaction as observed in Figure 4b. Figure 7b represents Tafel plots constructed from the data presented in Figure 7a. The Tafel slope values calculated were close to -60 mV dec^{-1} at low current densities and -120 mV dec^{-1} at high current density signifying the slow transfer of the first electron to the adsorbed oxygen molecule is the rate-determining step (rds). Similar findings regarding the ORR kinetics on supported Pt cathode catalysts have been reported earlier.^{62–65} Schmidt et al. defined the following elementary steps (2a-b) as the rds for the electroreduction of O₂ on Pt catalysts in alkaline media, which are more often written as a single-step reaction.⁶⁶

Specific activities calculated for all the catalysts at 0.9 V using Eq. 3 are listed in Table I.

$$\text{SA} = I_k/A_r \quad [3]$$

where I_k denotes the measured kinetic current. It was observed that 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst possesses remarkably higher SA value (0.22 mA cm^{-2}) than that of the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT (0.17 mA cm^{-2}), owing to the highly dispersed Pt NPs on the TiO₂/CNT composite as observed in the SEM and STEM images. A comparison of the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst to its 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT counterpart revealed that the latter showed a slight increase in the SA value as expected based on the Pt NPs supported on relatively thicker TiO₂ layer providing SMSI. The specific activities of 12Pt-35TiO₂/CNT (0.35 mA cm^{-2}) and Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT (0.30 mA cm^{-2}) are much higher than that of the Pt/C catalyst (0.20 mA cm^{-2}).

Figure 8. (a) Relative loss in the Pt surface areas of Pt-TiO₂/CNT and Pt/C during ADT; (b) ORR polarization curves recorded at 1900 rpm in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution before and after the stability test ($v = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$).

Mass activities of the catalysts were calculated using the equation below:

$$\text{MA} = I_k/m_{\text{Pt}} \quad [4]$$

where m_{Pt} represents the nominal Pt mass in the catalyst. The MA values calculated for all the prepared catalysts are given in Table I.

The highest MA of 124 A g^{-1} was shown by Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT, which is twofold higher than that of the commercial Pt/C (62 A g^{-1}). This can be ascribed to the dispersion of the Pt NPs on the TiO₂/CNT support as seen in Figure 1a. In the case of sputter-deposited Pt NPs, the mass activities of the catalysts followed nearly the same trend as that of the specific activities. It can be concluded that the deposition of Pt NPs and the metal-support interaction plays an important role in the ORR activity of Pt-TiO₂/CNT catalysts. For example, the higher mass activity of 4Pt-35TiO₂/CNT of 36 A g^{-1} in comparison to 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT (22 A g^{-1}) and 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT (25 A g^{-1}) can be described on the basis of deposition of the Pt nanoparticles and their interaction with the metal oxide. Similarly, 8Pt-50TiO₂/CNT catalysts appeared to be slightly more active than 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT that can be attributed to the relative thickness of the metal oxide coating.

Accelerated durability test (ADT).—Long-term durability of 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT catalysts was examined by measuring 10,000 potential cycles (0.6–1.0 V) at 100 mV s^{-1} in 0.1 M KOH solution. Relative loss in surface area of the catalyst during the ADT was determined from the hydrogen desorption peaks in the cyclic voltammograms recorded between 0.05 and 1.45 V at a potential sweep rate of 50 mV s^{-1} after each 1000th cycle. Figure 8a illustrates a comparison of the relative loss in the surface areas of the electrode during ADT. It can be seen that Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT and 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT are

more resistant to degradation retaining 77% and 74% of their real surface areas after 10,000 potential cycles, respectively. However, commercial Pt/C retained only 60% of its surface area, which is due to the relatively weaker interaction of the catalyst nanoparticles with the carbon support. The ORR activity was investigated by measuring RDE polarization curves at 1900 rpm in O₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH solution, before and after the durability test are presented in Figure 8b. It was found that the $E_{1/2}$ for Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT, 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT and Pt/C (20 wt%) decreased by 12, 22 and 108 mV, respectively. Similar results regarding durability of TiO₂ supported Pt NPs in comparison to Pt/C have been reported earlier.^{33,56,67} Shanmugam and co-workers have demonstrated that the Pt₈Ti-TiO₂/C catalyst is more durable than the commercial Pt/C.⁶⁸ Durability test of 3000 cycles between 0.1 and 1.3 V vs RHE at 50 mV s⁻¹ showed that Pt₈Ti-TiO₂/C catalyst retains 73% of its electrochemical surface area while commercial Pt/C retained only 10%. Our group has investigated the stability of Pt NPs deposited on graphene-TiO₂ composite.²⁵ We found relatively low durability of the prepared catalyst as compared to that of the commercial Pt/C, which might be associated with the weak anchoring of the Pt NPs on the TiO₂ coated graphene support. Similar studies on Nb-doped TiO₂ supported Pt catalyst have been reported by Elezovic et al.⁶⁴ They reported 4-electron reduction pathway of the Nb-TiO₂/Pt catalyst with comparable electrocatalytic activity to that of Pt/C catalyst toward O₂ reduction, 50 repetitive cycles in the potential range of 0.03–1.2 V at 100 mV s⁻¹ were performed, but it is not enough to investigate long-term durability of the catalyst. Interestingly, the specific activity of the 8Pt-35TiO₂/CNT catalyst increased from 0.16 to 0.25 mA cm⁻² with potential cycling, which might be because of the surface modification of the catalyst and development of more active sites during potential cycling.

Conclusions

Carbon nanotubes were decorated with titanium dioxide nanoclusters using the ALD technique. Thickness of the TiO₂ coatings was successfully controlled by the number of ALD cycles. Pt coatings of various thicknesses were deposited on the TiO₂/CNT composite using controlled sputter-deposition method. For comparison, Pt nanoparticles were also photo-deposited on the 35TiO₂/CNT support. SEM and TEM results confirmed uniform distribution of the Pt particles on the support surface, which confirms successful application of the two deposition techniques for the preparation of xPt-yTiO₂/CNT catalysts. Photo-deposition of Pt NPs facilitates Pt deposition on the metal oxide. The prepared Pt_{PD}-35TiO₂/CNT showed remarkably higher ORR activity in terms of mass-activity and half-wave potential. Moreover, xPt-yTiO₂/CNT type catalysts showed comparable ORR activity to Pt/C. It is concluded that the metal-support interaction plays an important role in the ORR activity of the supported Pt catalysts, which induces further investigations. Accelerated stability test showed that the Pt deposited on titanium dioxide-carbon composite is more stable than Pt/C.

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